

ANALYZING THE INFLUENCE OF TIKTOK AFFILIATE'S FACTORS ON THE CONSUMER PURCHASING INTENTION BETWEEN 20-30 YEAR-OLD TIKTOK USERS WITHIN METRO MANILA

Mary Joy Anne M. Martin, Sharnin Kyle M. Cañada, Julious I. Inolino,
Jerome S. Lumansoc, Patrick Jerome R. Ocan, Shane A. Satentes,
Antonio N. Taguinod Jr, Marianne A. Iban

*College of Business and Accountancy
Business Research
Our Lady of Fatima University*

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ABSTRACT

This research study is dedicated to understanding the multifaceted dimensions of consumer behavior of TikTok, focusing on the age demographic of 20 to 30-year-old users in the vibrant landscape of Metro Manila. The overarching objective is to scrutinize the network of factors affiliated with TikTok such as content quality, influencer credibility, audience engagement and product relevance that wield influence over the purchasing intentions of its users within this demographic. The research methodology encompasses a quantitative approach. Surveys will be conducted to gather firsthand insights from the 20 – 30 years-old users in the Metro Manila, offering deeper understanding of their interactions, perceptions, and decision-making processes within the TikTok environment. Statistical analysis will be employed to ascertain correlations and patterns between these factors and the observed purchasing intentions. Analysis showed after taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis; all factors: content quality (SD = 0.51), influencer credibility (SD = 0.48), audience engagement (SD = 0.48), product relevance (SD = 0.51), and purchase intention (SD = 0.51) were significant to the consumer's purchase intention. The study identified four crucial independent variables as major factors in this influence. Content quality, audience engagement, and product relevance all significantly influence consumer purchasing intention. This suggests that these factors are crucial considerations for TikTok affiliates

aiming to drive purchase decisions. While all independent variables demonstrated significant influence, influencer credibility emerged as the factor with the lowest, indicating its stronger and more specific association with consumer purchasing intention. This highlights the importance of building and maintaining trust and authenticity as a TikTok affiliate.

Keywords: *TikTok, TikTok Affiliates, Purchase Intention, Tiktok User, Content Quality, Audience Engagement, Product Relevance, Consumer Behavior, Influencer Credibility, Digital Marketing*

INTRODUCTION

In the age of social media marketing, TikTok affiliates have generated significant interest among businesses seeking innovative promotional approaches. TikTok, renowned for its short-form video content, has swiftly become a potent marketing platform, witnessing a surge in affiliate partnerships (Lauren Hallanan, 2018). These affiliates, primarily content creators or influencers, collaborate with brands to endorse products or services within engaging video content. Such collaborations on TikTok demonstrate substantial potential in driving consumer engagement and enhancing brand awareness. This growing trend of TikTok affiliates presents an intriguing landscape for exploring influencer marketing dynamics within this rapidly expanding social media platform. As social media platforms continue to evolve, TikTok's substantial user base and engagement rates have made it a focal point for affiliate marketing strategies (Jarboe, 2014). Influencers, capitalizing on their influence, join forces with brands to promote products or services, driving sales through unique and compelling content. A study by Influencer Marketing Hub reveals active engagement by TikTok creators in affiliate marketing, earning commissions based on sales generated from their promotional efforts. This trend underscores the platform's ability to foster profitable collaborations between influencers and brands, reshaping the digital marketing landscape in the realm of social media. Broken affiliate links is customers attempting to make purchases through affiliate promotions may become frustrated and have a bad experience due to broken links or outof-date codes, future purchases may be discouraged and brand perception may be harmed, restricted product information a few affiliate networks provide very little details on the goods they are promoting customers may find it challenging to make wise judgments as a result, and if their expectations aren't satisfied, they may become dissatisfied. The objectives of this study is to identify if attributes of a TikTok affiliate play a big role in shaping a customer's purchase intention. These goals include understanding audiences and identifying demographics such as age, gender, income, location, and other TikTok attributes. These goals include understanding audiences and identifying demographics such as age, gender, income, location, and other TikTok attributes. This study is significant because of various reasons; First, this research will provide insight into TikTok's function as a marketing platform and the impact of the TikTok affiliates' advertisements and videos that are put there on the age range of 20-30 years old's choice to make a purchase. Second, it will assist the marketing community such as affiliates in deciding whether or not to use the TikTok platform for product promotion, and if they will,

what factors to concentrate on while uploading their videos to produce an effective content. This study also supports existing hypotheses and other pertinent studies about the connection between TikTok users' purchase behavior and the TikTok platform as well as the TikTok affiliates.

Theoretical Framework

Customer-Centric Influencer Marketing (CIM)

In the customer centric influencer marketing model theory from Brown and Fiorella (2013), state that the orbit of the consumers influences the followers in making decisions when it comes to choosing a brand or product from TikTok affiliates. With this approach, TikTok affiliates can directly communicate with their followers that can possibly be their potential consumers as they use them to create content videos with creativity and spread their message that will result in the effectiveness of TikTok marketing strategies. The consumer cannot know about the actual product before buying the product or service experience and after-sales services; however, looking at the reviews of other consumers online, consumers' perceptions of quality, performance and post-purchase services can greatly impact their purchasing decisions as well as the reputation of brands. This has been supported by numerous studies including those conducted by Jalilv & Samiei (2012), Almana & Mirza (2013), Tham et al. (2013), Charo et al. (2015) and Sallam & Wahid (2015). Consumer Behavior Model.

Geyser (2022) emphasizes building relationships with influencers to effectively utilize social media marketing. Companies work with influencers to deliver interesting content that appeals to the audience they are targeting. By effectively employing influencers, businesses can drive brand awareness, increase sales, and foster customer loyalty. The user's stages of purchasing intentions are awareness, in which influencers introduce consumers to products or services through endorsements or promotions. Second is consideration, this is where consumers evaluate purchasing the product or service after learning more from influencers.

Lastly, the action where consumers take the step to purchase the product or service. The model also addresses influencer marketing challenges, such as identifying suitable influencers to partner with and measuring campaign effectiveness. Business must carefully

consider these challenges to successfully utilize influencer marketing and achieve their business objectives.

Geyser (2022)'s model provides a valuable framework for understanding how influencers influence consumer behavior. Businesses can develop effective influencer marketing campaigns that drive results by comprehending the different stages of the consumer decision-making process.

Literature Review

Content Quality

The influence of TikTok videos on consumer behaviour

As years pass, technology advances; businesses then adapt to the changes to achieve goals and objectives. From traditional advertising to digital marketing – online marketing, social media marketing, etc. Traditional advertising like newspapers was the major advertising method used to promote products and services, then television and radio advertising were introduced in the 19th century. To reach out to more markets and be accessible to all, the use of computers, smart phones, and the internet became prevalent as it is easy to access for both providers and users. The growth of technology affects the advancement of social media platforms. Now, social platforms can be used as a generator and way to share content such as text, videos, pictures which can be used for advertising products and services. As for marketing context, social media like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Pinterest, WhatsApp, TikTok and Snapchat is a platform where people interact by sharing information and opinions (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). According to a statistics report, in most countries, Facebook has the most monthly users with 3.58 billion. Also, TikTok is notably seen to have a growth in number of users and also use as a platform for sharing information and business.

Influencer Credibility

eWOM via the TikTok application and its influence on the purchase intention of Somethinc products

Electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) is a new phenomena that has emerged as a result of social media replacing conventional word-of-mouth (Hussain et al, 2017). According to data collected globally, there has been a noticeable increase in the number of consumer goods transactions made online, with many consumers basing their selections on the opinions of other web users, especially on social media. One of the most popular social media sites right now is TikTok, which features beauty-related material. One of the brands that is most popular on this application is Somethinc. The study found that marketers can amplify electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) by briefing influencers on what to include in their reviews. This allows marketers to control the content and better understand their customers. Additionally, marketers can learn from customer reviews to improve their products or develop new ones. The study also found that information quality, credibility, and quantity are important factors to consider when managing and marketing products.

Factors influencing the intention to use affiliate marketing: A conceptual analysis.

When a company uses third-party publishers who are vetted as affiliate marketers to advertise its products and services on its website, it is widely known as affiliate marketing (Zurina & Ong, 2019). Affiliate marketing, as defined by Fox and Wareham (2010), is the outsourcing of product selling by an organization, employing advertising channels like , text links, , text links, or banners. A commission is given to an affiliate when a customer clicks on the link (clicks), contacts the organization (leads), or makes a purchase (sale) of the recommended products. Dwivedi (2017) argue that affiliate marketing, categorized as result-driven online marketing, gauges success through the

amounts of revenue generated for the organization and commissions earned by the affiliate marketer. In essence, the growth in an organization's sales is a tangible indicator of affiliate marketing success, involving organizations, affiliate marketers, and customers, as highlighted by Mazurek and Kucia (2011).

Audience Engagement

The use of TikTok affiliate marketing for e-Commerce and online business

The study explores the potential of affiliate marketing as an innovative tool for enhancing brand value and boosting revenue. The findings reveal that TikTok affiliates marketing strategies can substantially elevate sales performance. Leveraging social media collaborations with celebrities enables businesses to reach a wider audience and promote their products effectively. This approach aligns with the growing prevalence of social media engagement, making it a powerful marketing strategy in the modern era. Examining the Shopee affiliate campaign, this study delves into the impact of TikTok social media marketing on impulsive purchases of fashion products, with hedonic shopping motivation serving as the intervening variable.

In accordance with Tuten (2008) as cited in Paurova & Gregova (2020), social media marketing is an online advertising form leveraging the cultural context of social communities, encompassing social networks, the visual realm, and social news sites to attain communication objectives and establish brand presence. Social media is made up of the words media and is a medium for interpersonal communication. Introduced in September 2016, TikTok is a social networking app enabling users to create, edit, and share videos with diverse filters and durations ranging from 15 seconds to 3 minutes. As per Hootsuite's data, TikTok stands as one of the most widely used social media platforms, securing the sixth position in popularity.

Bridging the empirical gap in the relationship and effect of TikTok on students' engagement: A case of a local college in the Philippines

The purpose of this research is to examine how individuals of different genders use and interact with TikTok and their engagement in class. The study also aims to investigate the relationship between the app's use and student engagement.

Based on the results, it is inferred that the strategic use of the app has the potential to enhance and influence students' participation and engagement. The study found that undergraduates at the college are responsible app users who do not want to be distracted from their studies. Students use TikTok as a form of stress relief and entertainment between classes and after completing coursework. The research suggests that collaboration between teachers and the College Guidance Office is necessary to provide guidance on the appropriate use of social networking apps in the classroom.

TikTok as a supplementary instructional material in teaching Filipino and communication subjects

In September 2016, the social networking app TikTok made its debut, offering users the capability to produce, edit, and share videos equipped with diverse filters and durations ranging from 15 seconds to 3 minutes. According to Hootsuite's data, TikTok

has secured the sixth position among the most popular social media platforms, showcasing its widespread acceptance.

High levels of mental and emotional effectiveness were observed when TikTok was employed as an innovative supplementary instructional tool, according to the study, as well as active learning among secondary and tertiary students. It also revealed a significant difference in students' performance, the study concluded that Supplementary material for teaching Filipino and Communication subjects was effectively enhanced through the incorporation of TikTok videos, encouraging teachers to explore similar innovative tools to improve student engagement and performance.

Effectiveness of brand ambassador on TikTok in the purchase intention of young professionals

Brand ambassadors, individuals compensated for endorsing products (Seldaña, 2019), hold a crucial role in shaping a positive brand image. The selection of well-regarded personalities by organizations contributes to a positive public perception, thereby enhancing the overall brand image. Companies often enlist the services of brand ambassadors for advertising their products, emphasizing the necessity for a high level of commitment and consistency in brand development.

In the current era of digitalization, leveraging brand ambassadors emerges as a strategic imperative for improving sales and fostering a positive image for company products. The surge in online transactions, accounting for a substantial 65.3% in 2018-2019, underscores the significance of digital marketing as a promising strategy. Notably, 33% of these transactions involved young individuals (Nisa & Pramesti, 2020).

Social media marketing activities, brand awareness, and brand image

A place where people may express their creativity and watch amusing, short films can be done in TikTok. By expressing themselves creatively, It is aimed at an audience that wants to entertain other audiences. According to Gesmundo et al (2022), TikTok is a creative expression platform. Johnson (2020) argues that with the people isolated, people now need to have a new way to interact with others and entertain themselves. TikTok has enabled countless users to create, watch videos, and promote businesses via short video content.

Product Relevance

The influence of TikTok videos on German Gen Z consumers' attitude and purchase intention towards sustainable brands

To acquire a commodity or service is the intention of a customer that is influenced by various advertising strategies, particularly on social media (Araujo et al. 2022). Social media has been recognized as an effective platform for product promotion, with studies supporting its utility (Alalwan et al. 2017; Duffett 2015; Wei & Jung 2017). On TikTok, common methods to stimulate consumer desire include advertising, live streaming, advertising and in-app purchases, and electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) (Zhuang 2022). Evidently, eWOM has become a strong advertising tool, especially among digitally informed customers, and research has explored its impact on consumer decision-making

(Tabassum et al. 2020). Notably, eWOM holds significance for Gen Z consumers, as they often rely on online reviews and recommendations when making purchase decisions (Khwaja et al. 2020).

In light of these findings, this research study delves into the influence of sustainable TikTok videos on purchasing intentions, exploring TikTok advertisements by sustainable brands and examining electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) concerning sustainable products, this study seeks to unravel the impact of information, trust, and entertainment on an individual's decision-making process when contemplating the purchase of a sustainable product.

Purchase Intention

Exploring the role of influencers and customers engagement on purchase intention in TikTok live streaming shopping

Examining the impact of influencer and customer engagement on the purchase intention of live-streaming shopping, with a focus on the TikTok platform, this study delves into the role of customer trust as a determinant of customer engagement. A significant impact on customers' purchase intention during live-streaming shopping on TikTok is notably unveiled by the research, with Influencer Credibility, including attractiveness, trustworthiness, and expertise, playing a crucial role. These findings align with prior research emphasizing the substantial impact of social media influencers on purchase intention, as demonstrated by Lim et al. (2017).

Investigating the determinants of customer engagement and purchase intention, this study unveils significant insights. Specifically, customer trust, spanning trust in community members, broadcast, and product, emerges as a pivotal factor impacting customer engagement. Moreover, the study underscores the influence of both customer engagement and influencers' credibility, encompassing attractiveness, trustworthiness, and expertise, on shaping purchase intention.

Purchasing Intention: A research on mobile phone usage by young adults

The primary goal of the research is to determine the variables that influence young adults' propensity to buy. An essential component in identifying the root causes of young adults' purchase intentions is the reference group. To avoid the hazards associated with purchasing unknown products, research indicates that young adults would rather purchase from trusted companies. From this vantage point, the study suggests a conceptual model that incorporates the structural connections among reference group, purchasing intention, and brand trust. By examining the moderating role of brand trust in this framework, the study hopes to add to the body of literature. A survey that 749 young individuals in Istanbul, Turkey, between the ages of 20 and 30 completed is used to evaluate a number of hypotheses. The AMOS-18 and IBM SPSS-23 programs were used to examine the data. Hierarchical regression analysis was done in addition to descriptive, reliability, and factor (exploratory and confirmatory) analysis in order to assess the research hypotheses. The findings indicate that purchasing intention is positively influenced by the reference group, and that this relationship is moderated by brand trust.

Marketing campaigns leading to the purchase of accommodation products

Social commerce has transformed how accommodations are marketed, leveraging online promotions, social media advertising, and the creation of web pages. Fundamentally, marketing influenced consumers to make purchases, and the advent of the internet led to the evolution of diverse marketing approaches. This study aimed to create an analysis centered on consumers' initial impressions of accommodation products in marketing campaigns.

Kariru (2022) highlights the significant influence of electronic technology on the evolution of digital marketing as a modern approach. The integration of diverse marketing tactics across online platforms, including the internet, social media, mobile devices, video content, affiliate marketing, and search engine optimization, stands as a crucial component of contemporary marketing strategy (Khan & Nawaz, 2021). Recognizing the potential for hoteliers to gain a competitive edge, this approach could ultimately contribute to the enhanced overall tourism performance in a given region (Kariru, 2022; Leite & Azevedo, 2017).

Muhammedrisaevna et. Al (2020) proposed that the internet holds the promise of creating opportunities for businesses by delivering tailored advertising to the right audience. The worldwide web enables businesses to gather feedback from consumers regarding promotional content. One remarkable feature highlighted here is the capacity to adjust an entire campaign's strategy during its ongoing execution. Song and Yoo (2016) have documented the significant influence of social media on customers' pre-purchase decision-making.

Influence of TikTok video advertisements on Generation Z's behavior and purchase intention

TikTok's dynamic and rapid algorithm has a strong appeal to young audiences worldwide (Weimann & Masri, 2021) due to its focus on short-form videos that promote joy and creativity. By April 2019, TikTok had experienced a remarkable 200% growth in market share within just two years, setting it apart from other social media platforms (Wang et al, 2020). TikTok, owned by ByteDance, has seen a massive surge in users and cultural significance, reflecting the youth's culture, rituals, spaces, and lifestyles (Kennedy, 2020). Remaining a conduit for businesses, it continues to facilitate connections with audiences through straightforward and scalable solutions (TikTok, 2021).

In the Philippines, the 18-24 age group makes up 31.7% of the total audience on TikTok, presenting a valuable target for marketers (Kemp, 2021). To engage Generation Z, it's essential for marketers to create content that is authentic and relatable (Khwaja et al., 2020). Chang (2020) noted that new media and their underlying technologies offer both opportunities and challenges for advertisers. Despite this, TikTok, when compared to established platforms like Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook is relatively unexplored in terms of its impact on marketing communication, consumer behavior, and purchase intention. Within this study, the spotlight is directed towards three dimensions of TikTok advertisements: emotional, entertaining, and informative. Emotional ads connect with the

audience on a personal level, while entertaining ads are visually appealing and lighthearted. Informative ads provide in- depth information about products and brands.

The impact of Digital Marketing on customer buying intention of customers in the Philippines

Consequently, the primary objective of this study is to investigate the connection between customer engagement and purchase intention, leading to the following hypothesis: H5: Customer engagement exerts a substantial influence on purchase intention (Husnain & Toor, 2017). In the current study, the focus is on how marketing, particularly through social media and email, influences consumer behavior, specifically in terms of customer engagement and purchase intention.

The study also found that Filipinos are influenced by online advertisements, and that digital marketing has a positive impact on customer engagement and purchase intentions. This is important for businesses to know, as it shows that they should focus on using digital marketing to reach their target audience.

Research Simulacrum

Figure 1. The Conceptual Model

The diagram shows that the Independent Variables which are the Content Quality, Influencer Credibility, Audience Engagement and Product Relevance are the four factors that the researchers considered to assess the TikTok users' Purchase Intention—the

Dependent Variable. These four independent variables are grounded in a comprehensive review of relevant academic research on TikTok users' Purchase Intentions.

Research Questions

Research Question no. 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents?

1.1 Age

1.2 Gender

Research Question no. 2: Do the four factors of TikTok affiliates have an impact on the purchasing intention of consumers living in Metro Manila?

2.1 Does Content Quality have a significant role on consumer's purchasing intention?

2.2 Does Influencer Credibility have a significant role on a consumer's purchasing intention?

2.3 Does Audience Engagement have a significant role on consumer's purchasing intention?

2.4 Does Product Relevance have a significant role on consumer's purchasing intention?

Research Question no. 3: Among all the variables, which one of them received the lowest score?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers employed a quantitative approach to create the research and collect data on the subject matter (Creswell, 2020). This method was used as it allowed them to collect and analyze huge amounts of data from a representative sample of the population, that is crucial for extrapolating the findings to a broader population. Quantitative research is a systematic, empirical approach to research that uses numerical data to collect and analyze information (Creswell, 2020). Quantitative research is particularly important in marketing research, as it allows researchers to gather insights into consumer behavior, preferences, and trends. A type of research that does not involve manipulating or controlling the variables being studied is called Non-experimental research (Creswell, 2020). Instead, researchers rely on observing and measuring the variables as they occur naturally. Non-experimental research can be used to study a wide range of phenomena, including consumer behavior, social trends, and the effects of public policies. Non-experimental research is a valuable tool for researchers in all fields, including marketing, because it allows them to study phenomena that cannot be easily manipulated or controlled. It is particularly important in marketing research as it allows researchers to understand consumer behavior and motivations in real-world settings.

Research Locale

The researchers strategically chose Metro Manila, a highly urbanized area which consists of 16 municipalities, as the study location due to its large student population, which guaranteed access to a sufficient number of participants. Additionally, its accessibility and practicality allowed for efficient data collection within a short timeframe. This strategic location facilitated swift and comprehensive data gathering from respondents residing in the areas of Metro Manila.

Population and Sampling

The researchers opted for purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling method, with Metro Manila selected as the target respondents. In this sampling, the researchers do not select participants randomly. Non-probability sampling is a sampling technique that does not involve random selection of participants. This implies that the likelihood of selection for the sample is not uniform across all members of the population. (Trochim, 2006, p. 103) Purposive sampling falls under the category of non-probability sampling in which the researchers select participants based on their specific needs for the study. Purposive sampling, enables researchers to choose participants who are most likely to provide the desired information." (Creswell, 2014, p. 152). In this case, the researchers will select participants based on their expertise, knowledge, or experience with TikTok Marketing. In order to compute the sample size that was used in the research and data gathering, the researchers used G-Power for having accurate number.

Research Instruments

Instruments are essential tools for measuring variables such as opinions, concepts, attitudes, and structures in educational research. The selection and use of appropriate research instruments is essential for conducting rigorous and informative research." (Trochim, 2006, p. 129). Questionnaires are effective examples of research instruments. This study will use online Google form with English and Tagalog transcriptions and are self-made by the researchers as they are easy to use to collect data and ask people questions. Additionally, the researchers used consent and screening tools to clarify their interest, notify respondents that their privacy and data are protected, and ensure that respondents are qualified to complete the research questionnaire. The questionnaires underwent with thorough validations and serious consultations after being approved and dispatched to the target respondents. Finally, the researchers used a Likert scale to measure respondents' level of preference.

Data Analysis

Data Analysis is an essential tool for anyone who wants to be able to make sense of data and use it to make better decisions. For example, data analysis can be used to identify trends and patterns in data that would be difficult or impossible to see with the naked eye (Brown, 2010). Several vital events occurred during the data analysis stage such as the

organization of data gathered, providing interpretations and the actual analysis of the data using SPSS data analysis tool. Analyzing the relationship between P value, Pearson Correlation and some other coefficients were extremely hard to analyze as those values has to be connected and related. Despite the limitations of non-probability sampling, it can be a useful tool for researchers who need to collect data from a specific population that is difficult to reach. In this study, the researchers used non-probability sampling to collect data from Metro Manila areas having the ages ranging from 20-30 years old.

RESULTS

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Demographic	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
20-30	107	100%
Gender		
Male	59.8	
		100%
Female	40.2	

The respondents included in this study comprised 107 individuals who actively engage with TikTok and reside in the bustling locales of Metro Manila, the Philippines' vibrant urban hub. These carefully selected participants fall within the age bracket of 20 to 30 years old, encapsulating a diverse spectrum of experiences and perspectives within this age group. Their inclusion in this research study represents a comprehensive and exhaustive 100% sample, ensuring a robust and holistic exploration of the trends and behaviors prevalent among this demographic in the context of TikTok usage within Metro Manila.

Table 2: Content Quality

Variables	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Regression Coefficient	Decision rule and Interpretation
Content Quality and Purchase Intention	0.707	<.001	0.289	Reject Ho1: Content Quality is a significant predictor in customer's Purchase Intention.

The table shows how Content Quality affects the Purchase Intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented in linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a P-Value of <.001. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result in the null hypothesis being rejected. As a result, Content Quality is a significant factor between consumer's Purchase Intention. There is also a high correlation (0.707) between two variables, and each unit of Content Quality has 0.289 increase in Purchase Intention.

Table 3: Influencer Credibility

Variables	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Regression Coefficient	Decision rule and Interpretation
Influencer Credibility and Purchase Intention	0.602	0.106	-1.23	Accept Ho2: Influencer Credibility is not a significant predictor in customer's Purchase Intention.

The table shows how Influencer Credibility affects the Purchase Intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented in linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a P-Value of .106. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result in the null hypothesis being accepted. As a result, Influencer Credibility is a significant factor between consumer's Purchase Intention. There is also a

moderate correlation (.602) between two variables, and each unit of Influencer Credibility has -1.23 decrease in Purchase Intention.

Table 4: Audience Engagement

Variables	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Regression Coefficient	Decision rule and Interpretation
Audience Engagement and Purchase Intention	0.823	<.001	0.362	Reject Ho3: Audience Engagement is a significant predictor in customer's Purchase Intention.

The table shows how Audience Engagement affects the Purchase Intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented in linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a P-Value of <.001. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result in the null hypotheses is being rejected. As a result, Audience Engagement is a significant factor for consumer's Purchase Intention. There is also a very high correlation (0.823) between two variables, and each unit of Audience Engagement has.

Table 5: Product relevance

Variables	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Regression Coefficient	Decision rule and Interpretation
Product Relevance and Purchase Intention	0.823	<.001	0.451	Reject Ho4: Product Relevance is a significant factor in customer's Purchase Intention.

The table shows how Product Relevance affects the Purchase Intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented in linear regression, with the

researchers obtaining a P-Value of $<.001$. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result in the null hypothesis being rejected. As a result, Product Relevance is a significant factor for consumer's Purchase Intention. There is also a very high correlation (0.823) between two variables, and each unit of Product Relevance has .451 increase in Purchase Intention.

Discussion

There are some parts in the results that are aligned with the previous studies that states that TikTok affiliates must have quality content in order for them to convert viewers into potential customers. On the other hand, one of the researcher's independent variable "Influencer Credibility" doesn't seem to match the previous studies as the results came out different. The results states that regardless of how popular the endorser is, it is not a huge factor that a customer is considering whenever they are making a purchasing decision.

The implications of these results are that Content Quality is an important factor that influences Purchase Intention. For businesses to truly connect with their audience, creating high-quality content is like building a bridge, carefully constructed to meet their needs on the other side. High-quality content can help to increase brand awareness, build trust with customers, and ultimately lead to more sales.

For Influencer Credibility, brands that are aiming to increase Purchase Intention through influencer marketing need to carefully select credible influencers who resonate with their target audience. High levels of perceived expertise, trustworthiness, and authenticity might not guarantee increased sales.

The findings emphasize the power of Audience Engagement as a critical driver of Purchase Intention. By proactively engaging your audience and creating meaningful connections, businesses can significantly increase their chances of customer conversion.

These findings emphasize the significance of Product Relevance in influencing purchase decisions. By prioritizing relevance in product development, marketing, and customer engagement, businesses can effectively drive up Purchase Intention and sales.

Conclusions

This research study determined the impact of Content Quality, Influencer Credibility, Audience Engagement and Product Relevance on the Purchase Intention of consumers ages 20-30 years old residing within Metro Manila. The rise of this dynamic social media platform has opened up an entirely new realm of marketing opportunities for businesses. This study enables to understand in a different views that an influencer holds many responsibilities that's make a phenomenon level of influence that influencers have

on their audience. In these circumstances, influencers value money and sponsorship. Rather than sharing products and brands that they stand behind, many influencers are eager to promote anything, as long as they are being paid. As per the study's results, the involvement of TikTok affiliates significantly impacted the buying intent of consumers aged 20-30 in Metro Manila. The study identified four crucial independent variables as major factors in this influence. Content Quality, Audience Engagement, and Product Relevance all significantly influence consumer Purchasing Intention among 20-30 year-old TikTok users in Metro Manila, with P-Values $<.001$. This suggests that these factors are crucial considerations for TikTok affiliates aiming to drive purchase decisions. While all independent variables demonstrated significant influence, Influencer Credibility emerged as the factor that exceeded the significance level indicating its weak association with consumer purchasing intention. The findings suggest that successful TikTok affiliate marketing strategies should enhance focus on Content Quality, Audience Engagement, and Product Relevance. In terms of Influencer Credibility, they should prioritize building and projecting strong image of their endorser.

Recommendations

The researchers made this study to assess the impact of TikTok affiliates to the purchasing intention of consumers aging from 20-30 within Metro Manila with the use of four different variables. The findings showed that The TikTok affiliates is an effective way for businesses to increase their sales and increase their brand's publicity, so that the business owners can efficiently utilize TikTok as a platform for marketing campaigns.

In addition to that, business owners can promote their products through this platform in order to reach their target market. The study also discovered that among the four variables assessed in TikTok affiliates, Influencer Credibility is the closest to the significance level, although the P-Value didn't exceed more than significance level, the researchers still recommends to business owners and marketers that Influencer Credibility should be taken more seriously in consideration in choosing the right and suited affiliate image on the products they are selling.

Content Quality Recommendation- Start-up owners should prioritize Content Quality. The impact of affiliate Content Quality on conversion rates can guide content creation strategies for attracting high-performing affiliates. Targeting niche influencers and fostering strong communication with affiliates are crucial, while offering competitive commissions and investing on high quality cameras and trendy backdrop technology for program management can further boost results. By collaborating on content, training affiliates on brand voice, and establishing clear quality criteria, start-ups can unlock the full potential of this powerful sales channel and drive growth by leveraging high-quality affiliate content.

Influencer Credibility Recommendation- Avoid fleeting fame by fostering long-term partnerships, co-creating impactful content, and tracking results. Open communication is key, hence providing clear guidelines while allowing artistic freedom

and offering ongoing support is a must. By investing in trust and authenticity, brands unlock the true power of influencers, turning campaigns into thriving testaments to credible collaboration. Pick influencers who truly connect with your target audience, rather than those with just a ton of followers. Look for experts in your field who consistently engage with their fans through high-quality, honest content that matches your brand.

Audience Engagement Recommendation- Maximize Audience Engagement on con through strategic hashtag utilization, trending challenge participation, and collaborative content creation. Foster a dynamic dialogue via interactive Q&A sessions, engaging polls, and responsive comment management. Drive conversions with clear calls to action, immersive live shopping features, and impactful influencer partnerships. Continuously optimize your strategy by meticulously analyzing performance data and adapting to evolving trends. By implementing these strategic directives, you can transform TikTok into a potent sales engine for your business.

Product Relevance Recommendation- Business owners should conduct continuous research on the trending products and on the products that seem to be popular sooner or later. By having these products initially studied, business owners can leverage their time thinking whether the product is worthy of their investment or not, hence lesser the risk. In addition, there are products that are only popular in short time due to being “Hyped” on social media platforms. Investing in research activities can not only save business and investors on money but also they can maximize their time to decide if they would pursue to sell the product or not.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adheres to strong ethical standards throughout. The authors ensured they obtained permission from all participants, emphasizing their freedom to leave the study at any time. Striving to protect everyone's privacy, measures were taken to keep participants' identities confidential. The well-being of the participants was a top priority. The authors took steps to create a safe and comfortable environment for them throughout the study. In maintaining transparency, the authors declare the absence of any personal gain or conflicts of interest during the study. Strict measures were taken to avoid copying or using others' work without proper credit. An unbiased approach was applied in interpreting the findings, ensuring fairness. The results obtained are solely used for research purposes, contributing to broader knowledge without personal bias or gain.

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Questionnaire

Content Quality *

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
<p>The content created by TikTok affiliates are relevant to my interests and needs. (Ang nilalaman ng mga bidyo na ginagawa ng mga TikTok affiliates ay may kaugnayan sa aking mga interes at pangangailangan.)</p>	☐	☐	☐	☐
<p>I am more invested in an affiliates' TikTok video if it shows important information about the product rather than being bland. (Mas naglalaan ako ng pansin sa bidyo ng TikTok affiliates kung ito ay nagpapakita ng mahahalagang impormasyon tungkol sa produkto kaysa sa pagiging walang saysay.)</p>	☐	☐	☐	☐

Quality such as clear audio make me interested in the affiliates' content.
(Ang mga katangian tulad ng magandang resolusyon at malinaw na audio ay nagpapakita ng interes sa akin sa nilalaman ng bidyo ng mga TikTok affiliates.)

The quality of a TikTok influencer marketing video affects how likely I am to buy the product they are endorsing.
(Ang kalidad ng isang marketing video ng mga TikTok influencer ay nakaaapekto kung gaano ko kagusto bumili ng produktong kanilang ini-endorso.)

I am driven by the TikTok affiliates' content if it uses storytelling techniques to promote products and services.
(Nahihikayat ako sa nilalaman ng bidyo ng mga TikTok affiliates kapag gumagamit ito ng mga teknik sa pagsasalaysay

Influencer Credibility *

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The TikTok affiliates' perceived trustworthiness influences my likelihood of engaging with their content and affiliate links. (Ang pagiging mapagkakatiwalaan ng mga TikTok affiliates ay nakaaapekto sa posibilidad na makipag-ugnayan ako sa nilalaman ng kanilang bidyo at affiliate links.)	☐	☐	☐	☐
The transparency of affiliates with products or services affects my purchasing intention. (Ang pagiging totoo ng mga TikTok affiliates tungkol sa kanilang mga produkto o serbisyo ay nakaaapekto sa aking intensyon na bumili.)	☐	☐	☐	☐

The influencer's product knowledge influences trust in their recommendations.
(Ang kaalaman ng influencer sa produkto ay nakaaapekto sa tiwala ko sa kanilang mga rekomendasyon.)

The influencer's lifestyle and branding should match the product they are marketing.
(Dapat tugma ang uri ng pamumuhay at pagba-brand ng influencer sa produktong kanilang ini-endorso.)

The credibility of TikTok affiliates influences my purchasing intentions.
(Ang kredibilidad ng mga TikTok affiliates ay nakaaapekto sa aking intensyon na bumili.)

Audience Engagement *

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The amount of audience engagement from an affiliate affects my purchasing intention. (Ang bilang o antas ng pakikilahok ng audience sa isang TikTok affiliate ay nakaaapekto sa aking intensyon na bumili.)	☐	☐	☐	☐
An influencer engaging with their audience convinces me to buy the product. (Ang pakikipag-ugnayan ng isang influencer sa kanilang audience ay nakakukumbinse sa akin na bumili ng produkto.)	☐	☐	☐	☐

The influencer's ability to answer questions regarding the product urges me to engage with them.

(Ang kakayahan ng isang influencer na sagutin ang mga tanong tungkol sa produkto ay nagtutulak sa akin na makipag-ugnayan sa kanila.)

My friends' opinions on TikTok affiliates' recommendations influence my purchasing decisions.

(Ang opinyon ng aking mga kaibigan tungkol sa mga rekomendasyon ng mga TikTok affiliates ay nakaaapekto sa aking mga desisyon na bumili.)

TikTok affiliates' product recommendations influence my own purchasing decisions as a TikTok user.

(Ang mga rekomendasyon sa produkto ng mga TikTok

Product Relevance *

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
<p>The relevance of the product is my main reason for purchasing it, regardless of the influencer's involvement. (Ang kaugnayan o pagiging angkop ng produkto ang pangunahing dahilan ko sa pagbili kahit na walang impluwensiya ng isang influencer.)</p>	☐	☐	☐	☐
<p>The products that TikTok affiliates promote are always relevant to my needs and interests. (Ang mga produkto na ini-endorso ng mga TikTok affiliates ay laging may kaugnayan sa aking mga pangangailangan at interes.)</p>	☐	☐	☐	☐
<p>Trendiness on TikTok has a significant positive influence on users' satisfaction with buying a product.</p>	☐	☐	☐	☐

(Ang kasikatan o pagiging uso ay may positibong epekto sa kasiyahan ng mga gumagamit ng TikTok sa pagbili ng isang produkto.)

The relevance of the product is highly influenced by the TikTok affiliates.
(Ang pagiging angkop ng produkto ay lubos na naapektuhan ng mga TikTok affiliates.)

TikTok affiliates help me discover new products that I would not have found otherwise.
(Ang mga TikTok affiliates ay tumutulong sa akin na matuklasan ang mga bagong produkto na hindi ko matatagpuan sa ibang paraan.)

Purchase Intention *

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I am likely to purchase a product that I have seen promoted by an affiliate of TikTok. (May posibilidad na ako ay bumili ng isang produkto na nakita kong ine-endorso ng isang TikTok affiliate.)	☐	☐	☐	☐
The TikTok videos created by affiliates have influenced my past purchasing decisions. (Ang mga bidyo na ginawa ng mga TikTok affiliates ay nakaimpluwensya sa aking mga nakaraang desisyon sa pagbili.)	☐	☐	☐	☐
I trust affiliates' recommendations and consider them when making purchasing decisions.				

(Nagtitiwala at kinokonsidera ko ang mga rekomendasyon ng mga TikTok affiliates at iniisip ko ang mga ito kapag gumagawa ng mga desisyon sa pagbili.)

I am more likely to purchase a product if it has been positively reviewed by an affiliate that I follow on TikTok. (Mas may posibilidad akong bumili ng isang produkto kung ito ay may positibong review mula sa isang TikTok affiliate na sinusundan o sinusubaybayan ko sa TikTok.)

TikTok affiliates have made me aware of new products and services that I would not have otherwise discovered. (Dahil sa mga TikTok affiliates naging maalam ako sa mga